

Appendix S6. Rank correlation between Bayesian and frequentist analyses.

Table S1: Comparisons of estimated genetic variances between the Bayesian pedigree (*MCMCglmm*), Bayesian family-level (*MCMCglmm*), and frequentist family-level models (*lme4*). All estimated genetic variances reported here are on the latent scale only; Data-scale values are provided in Table 3. Genetic variances are reported for each environment: the field and the greenhouse (G.H). The “broad-sense” genetic variance (“ V_G ”) from the Bayesian pedigree model is the sum of additive and dominance genetic variance (*i.e.*, $1/2V_A + 1/4V_D$).

Trait	Environment	Decomposed genetic variances from the full <i>MCMCglmm</i> model					Composite from full <i>MCMCglmm</i>	Simple from <i>lme4</i>	Simple <i>MCMCglmm</i>
		V_A	$1/2 V_A$	V_D	$1/4V_D$	V_M	" V_G "	V_G	V_G
Leaf number	Field	0.569	0.285	0.716	0.179	0.0281	0.463	0.42	0.45
	G.H	0.63	0.315	0.159	0.398	0.089	0.712	0.61	0.64
Height	Field	12.5	6.25	28.4	7.102	1.15	13.35	12.34	13.11
	G.H	51.2	25.64	62.4	15.6	8.32	41.23	37.49	39.83
Inflorescences	Field	0.028	0.014	0.05	0.0125	5.4e-3	0.0265	0.029	0.028
	G.H	7.5e-4	3.75e-4	0.0025	6.25e-4	3.66e-3	0.001	0.014	0.015
Siliques	Field	0.0685	0.0343	0.119	0.0297	0.022	0.064	0.083	0.07
	G.H	0.0617	0.0309	0.141	0.0352	7.4e-3	0.0661	0.063	0.056

Figure S3: Rank correlation of V_G estimates between (A) *lme4* and the simple *MCMCglmm* models, (B) the simple *MCMCglmm* and composite *MCMCglmm* models, and (C) *lme4* and the composite *MCMCglmm* models. Each point indicates a V_G estimate from the 2 corresponding models for a particular trait in a specific environment. All V_G estimates are plotted from the latent scale. Equations of the line are provided with a $y=0$ intercept, as well as R^2 values.